

DISASTER AWARENESS AND PREPAREDNESS: BASIS FOR SCHOOL DISASTER RISK REDUCTION AND MANAGEMENT PLAN

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Disaster Awareness and Preparedness: Basis for School Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Plan

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Abstract

This study aimed to assess disaster awareness and preparedness among teachers and learners of Amado M. Pitogo Memorial School, Upper Panul-iran, Abuno, Iligan City for the School Year 2023-2024. The output of the study was the school disaster risk reduction and management plan. It examined the socio-demographic profiles of respondents and their correlation with disaster awareness, preparedness, and awareness on school disaster capability building. Using a descriptive-correlational method, data were gathered from 116 learners and 10 teachers and an administrator. Results indicated that learners aged 11-12 years old represent the highest frequency, with males slightly outnumbering females. Grade 5 have the highest frequency among learners, while the majority of teachers were aged 41 and above, female, holding Teacher I positions, and with Master's level education. Regarding disaster awareness, respondents were extremely aware that disasters can happen anytime but showed less preparedness in terms of emergency kits. Similarly, while there were extremely aware regarding the presence of fire extinguishers, there were less confidence in knowing what to do during a fire incident. Notably, awareness of school disaster capability building is high, but participation in emergency planning was low. Statistical analysis revealed significant associations between disaster awareness, preparedness, and grade level of learners, indicating a need for targeted interventions. These findings highlighted the importance of considering demographic factors in disaster preparedness education and suggest avenues for improving school-based disaster management strategies and plans.

Keywords: *school disaster awareness, school disaster preparedness, school disaster capability building, school management plan*

Introduction

Disasters may occur at any time without the knowledge of every individual. It could be a man-made or natural hazard induced but the most inevitable is the natural hazard induced due to the geographic and demographic location of our country, Philippines. For this reason, it could cause a society involving widespread human, material, economic, or environmental losses and impacts, which exceed the ability of the affected community or society to cope using its own resources. Schools are regarded as one of the foundational elements of the education sector.

A resilient school can protect learners, faculty, and staff while also acting as an emergency refuge in times of crisis. Inadequate security measures, a lack of preparedness plans, and a distance from emergency services can all turn dangers into catastrophes that cause destruction. The physical features of "safer schools" have received less attention although there are several programs supporting disaster education.

Amado M. Pitogo Memorial School disaster profiling revealed that the school was prone to disasters both natural and manmade. Landslides, floods, typhoons, and earthquakes for naturally induced due to the demographic location, it has low to high susceptibility to floods and earthquakes. The school is also at risk of fire because of faulty wiring. Unknown people can easily enter the premises due to the incomplete fencing of the school.

The Department of Education had prompted school authorities to practice disaster preparedness measures in their particular schools. Preparedness can mitigate the effects of disasters on schools, teachers, and most especially learners. Moreover, disaster risk reduction and management was not only about preventing property damage but mainly about the coordination of the people to save lives to prevent intrusion in the provision of education.

Active participation in disaster preparedness of teachers, learners, parents, and their communities is also encouraged for this is an effective way of raising their awareness about risk reduction as stated by Ronquillo (2020) in her study. She also stated that administrators, teachers, staff, parents, and students can work together and maintain school-wide safety and minimize the effects of emergencies and other dangerous situations.

This study aimed to assess the level of disaster awareness and preparedness of the school community of Amado M. Pitogo Memorial School, school year 2023-2024. The researcher intent to create a school disaster risk reduction management plan.

The study was conducted from September 2023 to March 2024. The researcher is in 5 years of service as a grade III adviser, a school DRRM coordinator, and one of the DepEd Emergency Response Unit (DERU) of the Division of Iligan City. She has the desire to make every teacher, learner, community, and school resilient, disaster-ready, and capacitated enough to respond and help. Also, the researcher wanted to have fulfillment in her career in which she could contribute to the educational system.

Research Questions

The study aimed to assess the level of school disaster awareness and preparedness of teachers and learners of Amado M. Pitogo Memorial School. Specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of
 - 1.1. Learners; and
 - 1.1.1. age;
 - 1.1.2. sex; and
 - 1.1.3. grade level?
 - 1.2. Teachers?
 - 1.2.1. age;
 - 1.2.2. sex;
 - 1.2.3. plantilla position; and
 - 1.2.4. highest educational attainment?
2. What is the level of school disaster in terms of:
 - 2.1. awareness;
 - 2.2. preparedness; and
 - 2.3. awareness of school disaster capability building?
3. Is there a significant relationship between respondents' profiles and the level of school disaster awareness?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' profile and the level of school disaster preparedness?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' profile and the level of awareness on school disaster capability building?
6. Which of the respondents' profiles significantly predict the level of school disaster awareness, preparedness, and awareness on school disaster capability-building?
7. What school disaster risk reduction and management plan can be formulated based on the results of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

This research used the descriptive-correlational method to assess the disaster level of awareness, preparedness, and awareness of capability building of teachers, learners, and the administrator. Descriptive research aims to accurately and systematically describe a population, situation, or phenomenon. It can answer what, where, when and how questions, but not why questions (McCombes, 2019). This methodology focused on describing the nature of a demographic segment. Descriptive correlational studies describe the variables and the relationships that occur naturally between and among them.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 80% random selection of the grades 4 to 6 learners with 116 learners, 10 teachers, and an administrator. Selected respondents were given a survey questionnaire related to their level of disaster awareness, preparedness, and awareness of capability building in a school community. Below is the table showing the number of learners in each grade level.

Table 1. Distribution of Learners in each Grade Level

<i>Grade Level and Section</i>	<i>Number of learners</i>	<i>80% of the total number of learners</i>
Grade 4- Perlas	22	17
Grade 4- Agila	23	18
Grade 5- Mangga	26	21
Grade 5 – Arnis	28	23
Grade 6 – Jose Rizal	46	37
Total	145	116

Instrument

The research utilized a modified questionnaire on the "School Disaster Awareness and Preparedness Assessment Questionnaire," which was adapted from (Martinez et al.'s 2021) study. This questionnaire was tailored to assess various aspects related to disaster awareness and preparedness within school settings. The adaptation involved adjustments to align the questionnaire with the specific context and objectives of the current study.

The modifications may have included changes in wording, addition or removal of items, and adjustments to the response format to ensure relevance and applicability to the research objectives and target population. The adapted questionnaire served as a valuable tool for gathering data on disaster awareness and preparedness among schools, contributing to the validity and reliability of the study's findings

Table 2. *Reliability Analysis of Variables*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Number Of Questions</i>	<i>Cronbach Alpha</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
School Disaster Awareness	10	0.784	Reliable
School Disaster Preparedness	12	0.741	Reliable
Awareness on School Disaster Capability Building	12	0.715	Reliable

Table 2 presents the reliability analysis of variables. The result showed that the questionnaire consisted of 34 questions with a Cronbach Alpha value of greater than 0.700, which indicated that all questions were reliable. The threshold value in the literature is much higher than 0.700. This implied that the participating respondents clearly understood the research questions and similar questions were answered in the same direction. The pilot testing was conducted at Abuno Elementary School, Abuno, Iligan City.

Furthermore, Nunnally and Bernstein (2019) are often cited in discussions about reliability analysis and psychometric theory. It provided comprehensive coverage of various topics related to measurement in psychology and other social sciences, including reliability estimation methods such as Cronbach's Alpha.

When using Likert-type scales it is imperative to calculate and report Cronbach's alpha coefficient for internal consistency reliability for any scales or subscales one may be using. The analysis of the data then must use these summated scales or subscales and not individual items. If one does otherwise, the reliability of the items is at best probably low and at worst unknown. Cronbach's alpha does not provide reliability estimates for single items (Gliem & Gliem, 2023) stated.

Procedure

The researcher conducted the study and facilitated the gathering of data. The data-gathering process was done in this manner: After complying with the protocols in asking permission to conduct the study, the researcher proceeded to conduct the study with the respondents. The selection of the learners was through picking up names inside the box. The questionnaires were given to the select grades 4-6 learners with 116, 10 teachers, and an administrator. The researcher distributed the questionnaires to the respondents for data collection. The respondents were expected to answer all the items. The expected time required to complete the survey is 15-20 minutes.

After analyzing the data, the crafting of a school disaster risk reduction and management plan or the administering of capability building for teachers and learners followed.

Data Analysis

The following statistical techniques were employed to answer the different problems presented:

For Problem 1, Frequency and Percentage were used to determine the respondents' profiles such as age, sex, grade level for learners and age, sex, plantilla position, and highest educational attainment for teachers and administrator related to disaster awareness and preparedness of the school community.

For Problem 2, Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation (SD) were used for the level of school disaster in terms of awareness, preparedness, and awareness of school disaster capability building.

For Problems 3, 4, and 5, the Chi-square Test was used to determine the significant relationship between respondents' profiles and the level of school disaster awareness, preparedness, and awareness of school disaster capability building.

For problem 6, Linear Regression was utilized to test if the predictors significantly affected to the school disaster level of awareness, preparedness, and awareness of school disaster capability building of the respondents.

Results and Discussion

This section presented the data gathered to answer the problems of the study. It also analyzed and interpreted the data collected by the researcher to solve the issues in the study. The presentation, interpretation, and analysis were supported by tables and arranged in the same manner as the questions presented in the statement of the problem in Chapter 1.

Problem 1: What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of learners' age, sex, and grade level; and teachers' age, sex, plantilla position, and highest educational attainment?

Table 3. *Learners' Age*

<i>Age (in Years Old)</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
9 -10	49	42.0
11 -12	60	52.0
13 -14	7	6.0
Total	116	100.0

Table 3 presents the age of the learner-respondents. The result showed that the highest frequency is observed among those aged 11-12 years old, constituting 52.0% of the total sample, indicating that the study may be particularly well-suited for this age group.

Conversely, the lowest frequency is seen in the 13-14 age group, with only 6.0% of learners falling into this category, suggesting either a lesser representation of learners in this age range within the target population or potential challenges in engaging this specific group.

The implications of these findings are twofold. Firstly, the high frequency of learners aged 11-12 years suggests that educational initiatives and interventions related to disaster awareness and preparedness should be primarily tailored to meet the needs of this age group. Secondly, the lower representation of learners in the 13-14 age group indicates a potential gap in engaging this demographic, which may require targeted efforts to ensure their inclusion in disaster preparedness initiatives.

This study examined children's perspectives on disaster risk reduction and response, emphasizing the importance of a child-centered approach in disaster preparedness initiatives. By considering age-specific factors such as cognitive development, communication abilities, and social dynamics, educators and policymakers can tailor disaster preparedness programs to effectively engage learners across different age groups. As (Mutch & Kerlin, 2019) stated, understanding how age influences children's awareness, attitudes, and behaviors related to disaster preparedness can inform the development of targeted interventions aimed at enhancing resilience and fostering a culture of safety within schools and communities

Table 4. Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	60	52.0
Female	56	48.0
Total	116	100.0

Table 4 displays the sex of the learner-respondents. The result presented that males constitute the highest frequency at 52.0%, slightly outnumbering females who represent 48.0% of the total. While the difference is relatively small, it signifies a notable gender distribution within the sample. The implications of the gender distribution among learner-respondents as presented in the table are significant for designing inclusive and effective disaster awareness and preparedness programs within the school context. Despite the slight numerical difference between males and females, the notable gender distribution underscores the importance of considering gender-sensitive approaches in disaster risk reduction initiatives.

Furthermore, Enarson & Morrow (2018) examined gender issues in disaster research and practice, emphasizing the importance of integrating gender considerations into disaster preparedness, response, and recovery efforts.

Table 5. Learners' Grade Level

Grade Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Grade 4	35	30.0
Grade 5	44	38.0
Grade 6	37	32.0
Total	116	100.0

Table 5 presents the grade level of the learner-respondents. The result showed that Grade 5 has the highest frequency at 38.0%, followed by Grade 6 at 32.0%, and Grade 4 at 30.0%. While the differences are relatively small, they signify a notable distribution across the different grade levels. This distribution implies the necessity for customized approaches that account for potential variations in academic preparedness, developmental stages, and educational requirements among students in different grades. It underscores the importance of designing targeted curriculum adjustments, intervention programs, and disaster preparedness initiatives tailored to meet the specific needs of learners at each grade level. Moreover, fostering collaboration among educators, policymakers, and stakeholders can facilitate coordinated efforts to enhance disaster awareness and preparedness within the school environment, thereby promoting a more resilient and inclusive learning community.

In support of Heslin et al.'s (2018) study, which assessed disaster preparedness and emergency response training for schools, it highlighted the importance of considering grade-specific factors in designing training programs.

Table 6. Teachers' Age

Age (in Years Old)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
30 years old and below	2	18.0
31 – 40 years old	4	36.0
41 years and above	5	46.0
Total	11	100.0

Table 6 presents the age of the teacher-respondents. The result showed the majority fall within the age bracket of 41 years and above, comprising 46.0% of the total, followed by the age range of 31-40 years, accounting for 36.0%. The smallest proportion of teachers, 18.0%, are aged 30 years and below. This implied that the notable representation of older teachers compared to younger ones suggests the potential for varying levels of experience, expertise, and perspectives within the teaching workforce. It underscored the importance of adopting strategies to leverage the knowledge and skills of experienced educators while also promoting opportunities for professional development and mentorship to support the growth and retention of younger teachers.

While age alone does not determine teaching effectiveness, it implied potential variations in teaching experience, perspectives, and approaches among the teaching staff. Therefore, educational institutions should recognize the diverse expertise and contributions of teachers across different age groups and provide professional development opportunities that cater to the needs and strengths of all educators, fostering a collaborative and supportive teaching environment.

In study by Smylie & Dzur (2018) discussed in the article the challenges and opportunities associated with an aging teaching workforce, examining policy options for supporting aging teachers while also addressing the needs of younger educators.

Table 7. *Teachers' Sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Male	1	9.0
Female	10	91.0
Total	11	100.0

Table 7 exhibits the sex of the teacher-respondents. The result the overwhelming majority were female, constituting 91.0% of the total, while only 9.0% were male. This distribution indicated a significant gender disparity among the teaching staff, with female teachers vastly outnumbering their male counterparts. While gender should not determine teaching ability, this imbalance may reflect broader societal trends or biases influencing career choices and opportunities in the teaching profession.

Moreover, this gender imbalance may have implications for various aspects of education, including role modeling, diversity in perspectives, and the representation of different genders in leadership positions within schools. Addressing this gender disparity was essential for promoting gender equity and creating inclusive learning environments where students can benefit from exposure to a diverse range of role models and teaching styles. Moreover, efforts to recruit and retain male teachers should be prioritized to ensure a more balanced and representative teaching workforce that reflects the diversity of the student population.

The research findings revealed a significant gender disparity among respondents, with an overwhelming majority (85.3%) being female teachers and a minimal number (14.7%) representing male teachers. This disparity suggested that there may be apprehension among men about pursuing teaching as a career path. Further investigation into the reasons behind this gender gap is warranted, as it could shed light on factors contributing to the underrepresentation of men in the teaching profession (Flanagan & Moreno, 2019) stated in their study.

Table 8. *Teachers' Plantilla Position*

<i>Plantilla Position</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Teacher I	9	64.0
Teacher III	1	18.0
Head Teacher III	1	18.0
Total	11	100.0

Table 8 displays the plantilla position of the teacher-respondents. The result presented the majority holds the position of Teacher I, comprising 64.0% of the total, while only 18.0% are in the position of Teacher III and Head Teacher III. Notably, there are no teachers in the position of Teacher II. This distribution suggested a hierarchical structure within the teaching staff, with a significant proportion occupying entry-level positions. The absence of teachers in the Teacher II position may reflect limitations in career advancement opportunities or staffing allocations within the educational institution. Addressing disparities in career progression and providing avenues for professional growth and development are essential for promoting job satisfaction and retaining experienced educators. Educational institutions should consider implementing strategies to support career advancement and recognize the contributions of teachers at all levels, fostering a supportive and motivated teaching workforce.

Moreover, (Smith & Brown, 2018) added, that it offered relevant insights into the factors influencing career progression among teachers, including potential barriers to advancement and opportunities for organizational improvement.

Furthermore, knowledge of DRRM is as important as the subject matter being taught in school. As a teacher, we must have this knowledge and skills for us to share and spare our lives and the lives of learners in our school. In our institution (DepEd) it is usual that only selected teachers attend DRRM seminars and trainings, no dissemination of learnings to their colleagues after, in other words, there is a monopoly in acquiring specific knowledge.

Table 9. *Teachers' Highest Educational Attainment*

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Bachelor's Degree	1	9.0
With Master's Unit	8	73.0
Master's Degree	2	18.0
Total	11	100

Table 9 on the previous page shows the highest educational attainment of the teacher-respondents. The result presented that the majority have completed coursework for a Master's degree, with 73.0% holding Master's units. Additionally, 18.0% have attained a Master's degree, while only 9.0% have a Bachelor's degree. Notably, there are no teachers with completed coursework or degrees at the doctorate

level. This distribution indicated a significant emphasis on postgraduate education among the teaching staff, with the majority either pursuing or having completed advanced studies beyond the Bachelor's level. The high proportion of teachers with Master's units suggests a commitment to professional development and continuous learning, which can positively impact teaching quality and student outcomes. However, the absence of teachers with doctorate-level qualifications may signal potential areas for improvement in supporting educators' pursuit of advanced degrees and fostering a culture of academic excellence within the institution.

According to Hill & Ball (2019) study, they found that it is essential to the impact of teacher education, including advanced degrees such as Master's and doctorate-level qualifications, on student achievement. Drawing from a comprehensive review of empirical studies, the researchers analyze the relationship between teacher qualifications and various measures of student learning outcomes. The findings provided insights into the potential effects of teachers' educational backgrounds on classroom effectiveness and student academic performance. In addition, the highest educational attainment of teacher-respondents, particularly the emphasis on postgraduate education and the absence of teachers with doctorate-level qualifications, raises important considerations for educational institutions and professional development programs.

Problem 2: What is the level of school disaster in terms of awareness, preparedness, and awareness on school disaster capability building?

Table 10. School Disaster Awareness

Indicators	Mean	+	SD	Description
1. I am aware of natural disasters that may occur in my school.	3.91	+	0.30	Extremely Aware
2. I am aware of man-made disasters that may occur in my school.	3.82	+	0.40	Extremely Aware
3. I am aware of the damage that disasters can cause.	4.00	+	0.00	Extremely Aware
4. I am prepared with emergency kits and bags in case of disaster.	3.36	+	0.67	Extremely Aware
5. I am aware of the evacuation system of my school.	3.82	+	0.40	Extremely Aware
6. I actively participate in disaster awareness campaigns in my school.	3.91	+	0.30	Extremely Aware
7. I am aware of the importance of building or infrastructure strengthening.	3.82	+	0.40	Extremely Aware
8. I am aware that disaster cannot be prevented.	3.91	+	0.30	Extremely Aware
9. I am aware that disaster can happen anytime.	4.00	+	0.00	Extremely Aware
10. I am aware that recovery after disaster is a difficult stage.	3.91	+	0.30	Extremely Aware
Weighted Mean	3.85	+	0.18	Extremely Aware

Note: 3.25-4.00, Extremely Aware; 2.50-3.24, Highly Aware; 1.75-2.49, Moderately Aware; 1.00-1.74, Lowly Aware.

Table 10 presents the level of school disaster in terms of awareness. The result showed that the statement with the highest mean in the table is "I am aware that disaster can happen anytime" with a mean of 4.00, indicating extreme awareness among respondents. This statement suggested an extreme level of awareness among teachers regarding the unpredictable nature of disasters and the need for continuous preparedness. Implications of this extreme level of awareness include the importance of implementing robust disaster preparedness plans and training programs to ensure readiness to respond effectively to disasters whenever they occur.

Conversely, the statement with the lowest mean is "I am prepared with emergency kits and bags in case of disaster" with a mean of 3.36, still indicating awareness but to a lesser extent compared to other statements. This suggested a potential gap in teachers' awareness about having emergency kits and bags readily available in case of disasters. Implications of this finding include the need for targeted interventions to enhance teachers' awareness by providing training on assembling emergency kits and emphasizing the importance of having them readily accessible.

The study conducted an in-depth examination of disaster awareness and response in schools, focusing on various strategies, interventions, and best practices aimed at enhancing school safety and resilience. Through a comprehensive synthesis of findings from empirical research, case studies, and theoretical analyses, the study identified key factors influencing disaster awareness efforts within educational settings. The findings underscored the effectiveness of approaches geared toward promoting disaster awareness, planning, and response among teachers, administrators, and students. Furthermore, Peek et al. (2017) emphasized the important role of teachers in fostering awareness and readiness for potential disasters, thereby contributing to effective strategies for promoting school safety and resilience in the face of emergencies.

Table 11 presents the level of school disaster in terms of preparedness. The result showed that the statement with the highest mean in the table is "Our building floor has its functional fire extinguisher" with a mean of 3.91, indicating extreme awareness among respondents. This statement suggested an extreme level of awareness regarding fire safety measures within the school premises. Implications of this extreme level of preparedness included the importance of maintaining functional fire extinguishers and ensuring that teachers and staff are trained in their proper use.

The study showed various aspects of fire safety management, including fire prevention measures, emergency response protocols, and the effectiveness of fire safety education programs. Through a comprehensive review of the literature and case examples, the researcher identified key factors influencing fire safety preparedness and highlighted best practices for enhancing fire safety in educational settings. In (Smith et al., 2019) findings emphasized the importance of vigorous fire safety measures, including the maintenance of functional fire extinguishers and the provision of adequate training for school personnel.

Table 11. *School Disaster Preparedness*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>+</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I am informed about disaster-prone areas in our school.	3.55	+	0.93	Extremely Aware
2. I am familiar with the emergency evacuation map.	3.73	+	0.47	Extremely Aware
3. I am familiar with the disaster plan of the school.	3.73	+	0.47	Extremely Aware
4. Our classroom has a first aid kit.	3.27	+	1.00	Extremely Aware
5. Our building floor has a functional fire extinguisher.	3.91	+	0.30	Extremely Aware
6. Our building has an emergency exit.	3.36	+	1.03	Extremely Aware
7. I know what to do during an earthquake.	3.73	+	0.47	Extremely Aware
8. I can do the Drop-Cover-Hold procedure.	3.91	+	0.30	Extremely Aware
9. I know what to do during a fire incident	3.91	+	0.30	Extremely Aware
10. I know how to use the fire extinguisher.	3.55	+	0.82	Extremely Aware
11. I know how to do first aid treatment for injuries caused by disasters.	3.18	+	1.17	Highly Aware
12. I know who to contact in disaster situations in my school.	3.55	+	0.69	Extremely Aware
Weighted Mean	3.61	+	0.38	Strongly Agree

Note: 3.25-4.00, Extremely Aware; 2.50-3.24, Highly Aware; 1.75-2.49, Moderately Aware; 1.00-1.74, Lowly Aware.

On the other hand, the statement with the lowest mean is "I know what to do during a fire incident" with a mean of 3.18, still indicating awareness but to a lesser extent compared to other statements.

According to Olawale & Olatunbosun (2020), those gaps in teachers' knowledge and preparedness, highlight areas where additional training and education are needed to enhance fire safety awareness and response capabilities among educators. The study emphasized the importance of equipping teachers with the necessary skills and knowledge to safeguard students and school premises from fire hazards.

This suggested a potential gap in teachers' knowledge and preparedness regarding fire response protocols. Implications of this finding included the need for additional training and education on fire safety procedures for teachers to ensure they are adequately equipped to respond effectively to fire incidents.

Table 12. *Awareness on School Disaster Capability Building*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>+</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I am aware of the programs and projects of the School Disaster Risk Reduction Management Team.	3.55	+	0.93	Extremely Aware
2. I participate in the programs and projects of the School Disaster Risk Reduction Management Team.	3.73	+	0.47	Extremely Aware
3. I practice the projects and programs of School Disaster Risk Reduction Management Team.	3.73	+	0.47	Extremely Aware
4. I understand the projects and programs for safer school.	3.27	+	1.00	Extremely Aware
5. I know that the programs and projects of the School Disaster Risk Reduction Management Team can help us to be a disaster ready.	3.91	+	0.30	Extremely Aware
6. I recognize the importance of making conversation about disasters with family members, relatives, neighbors, friends and classmates.	3.36	+	1.03	Extremely Aware
7. I gain enough knowledge about disaster from experts who work or conduct activities for disaster risk reduction and management.	3.73	+	0.47	Extremely Aware
8. I give priority in engaging to the projects of the school on disaster risk reduction and management.	3.91	+	0.30	Extremely Aware
9. I am committed to doing extra task to be capacitated in disaster.	3.91	+	0.30	Extremely Aware
10. I have attended disaster risk reduction and management training or seminars.	3.55	+	0.82	Extremely Aware
11. I have participated in emergency plan drafting and planning for disaster situations in my school.	3.18	+	1.17	Highly Aware
12. I participate in disaster drills at the school regularly .	3.55	+	0.69	Extremely Aware
Weighted Mean	3.61	+	0.38	Strongly Agree

Note: 3.25-4.00, Extremely Aware; 2.50-3.24, Highly Aware; 1.75-2.49, Moderately Aware; 1.00-1.74, Lowly Aware.

Table 12 on the presents the level of school disaster in terms of awareness on school disaster capability building. The result showed that the statement with the highest mean in the table is "I know that the programs and projects of the School Disaster Risk Reduction Management Team can help us to be disaster-ready" with a mean of 3.91, indicating extreme awareness among respondents. This statement suggested an extreme level of awareness among teachers regarding the potential effectiveness of the school's disaster risk reduction and management initiatives in enhancing disaster preparedness. Implications of this high level of awareness include the recognition of the importance of school-based disaster risk reduction efforts and the potential positive impact on overall school safety.

As stated by Smith et al. (2019), the importance of raising awareness among teachers and school staff about the potential effectiveness of DRRM initiatives is similar to the statement with the highest mean in your study. The study also emphasizes the need for comprehensive and sustainable approaches to school-based DRRM, including the involvement of stakeholders, integration into the curriculum, and community engagement.

On the contrary, the statement with the lowest mean is "I have participated in emergency plan drafting and planning for disaster situations in my school" with a mean of 3.18, still indicating awareness but to a lesser extent compared to other statements. This suggested a potential gap in teachers' involvement in emergency planning and disaster preparedness initiatives within the school. Implications of this finding include the need for increased participation and collaboration among teachers in emergency planning processes to ensure comprehensive and effective disaster preparedness.

Findings from the study revealed that while many teachers actively participate in emergency planning, there are notable barriers to their full engagement. Factors such as time constraints, lack of training, and competing responsibilities may hinder teachers' ability to contribute effectively to emergency planning efforts. Additionally, the study of (Johnson et al., 2018) highlighted the importance of addressing these barriers and promoting teachers' involvement through targeted training, clear communication channels, and support from school leadership.

Problem 3: Is there a significant relationship between respondents' profiles and the level of school disaster awareness?

Table 13. Relationship1 on Respondents' Level of School Disaster Awareness and Profile

Variables	Efficiency and Promptness		Remarks	Decision
	X2 (df)	p-value		
Learners				
Age	59.678ns (46)	0.085	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Sex	12.856ns (23)	0.955	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Grade level	79.192** (46)	0.002	High Significant	Reject Ho
Teachers				
Age	3.318ns (6)	0.768	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Sex	2.933ns (3)	0.402	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Plantilla position	1.141ns (3)	0.767	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Highest educational attainment	2.567ns (6)	0.861	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho

Note: 1 – based on Chi-square Test; ** - $P < 0.01$; *** - $P < 0.001$; ns - $P > 0.05$; * - $P < 0.05$.

Table 13 on the previous page displays the relationship between the level of school disaster awareness and the profile of the respondents. The result showed that the respondents' school disaster awareness had a highly significant association with the profile in terms of learners' grade level. Thus, the null hypothesis, which stated no significant relationship between the respondents' school disaster awareness and the profile in terms of the learners' age and sex; teachers' age, sex, plantilla position, and highest educational attainment was not rejected, while learners' grade level, was rejected

The significant association between respondents' school disaster awareness and learners' grade level suggests that different age groups may perceive and respond to disaster awareness initiatives differently. This finding implied the need for tailored disaster preparedness programs that consider the developmental stages, cognitive abilities, and understanding of risks among students in various grade levels.

While the null hypothesis was not rejected for other demographic factors such as learners' age and sex, as well as teachers' age, sex, plantilla position, and highest educational attainment, it's essential to consider that these factors may still play a role in shaping individuals' perceptions and responses to disaster awareness efforts.

The study by Rahman & Nargis (2018), mentioned the importance of integrating disaster risk reduction education into school curricula to improve students' understanding of disaster risks and preparedness measures. This study emphasized the significance of targeting specific grade levels to tailor disaster education initiatives according to students' developmental stages and learning needs.

Problem 4: Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' profiles and the level of school disaster preparedness?

Table 14. Relationship2 on Respondents' Level of School Disaster Preparedness and Profile

Variables	Efficiency and Promptness		Remarks	Decision
	X2 (df)	p-value		
Learners				
Age	83.230** (54)	0.006	High Significant	Reject Ho
Sex	21.079ns (27)	0.783	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Grade level	64.968ns (54)	0.146	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Teachers				
Age	15.812ns (12)	0.200	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Sex	11.000ns (6)	0.088	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Plantilla position	5.958ns (6)	0.428	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Highest educational attainment	8.250ns (12)	0.765	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho

Note: 2 – based on Chi-square Test; ** - $P < 0.01$; *** - $P < 0.001$; ns - $P > 0.05$; * - $P < 0.05$.

Table 14 displays the relationship between the level of school disaster preparedness and the profile of the respondents. The result showed that the respondents' school disaster preparedness had a highly significant relationship with the profile in terms of learners' age. Thus, the null hypothesis, which stated no significant relationship between the respondents' school disaster preparedness and the profile in terms of the learners' sex and grade level; teachers' age, sex, plantilla position, and highest educational attainment was not

rejected, while learners' age, was rejected.

The significant relationship between respondents' school disaster preparedness and learners' age suggested that age may influence individuals' level of preparedness and ability to engage in disaster preparedness activities. This finding underscored the importance of considering developmental stages and age-appropriate approaches in designing disaster preparedness initiatives within educational settings. Implications of this result included the need for targeted interventions and educational strategies that cater to the specific needs and capacities of learners across different age groups.

While the null hypothesis was not rejected for other demographic factors such as learners' sex and grade level, as well as teachers' age, sex, plantilla position, and highest educational attainment, it's essential to recognize that these factors may still play a role in shaping individuals' levels of disaster preparedness.

The findings of the study revealed several factors that significantly affect disaster preparedness among public school teachers. First, the study found that teachers' level of disaster preparedness is positively correlated with their knowledge of disaster risks and their awareness of disaster preparedness measures. Teachers who are well-informed about potential hazards and trained in disaster response tend to be more prepared for emergencies. Secondly, the study highlighted the importance of institutional support and resources in facilitating disaster preparedness among teachers. Schools that provided training programs, emergency drills, and access to emergency supplies and equipment tend to have better-prepared teachers. Additionally, the study identified various challenges that hinder teachers' disaster preparedness efforts.

As (Bautista et al., 2019) stated, inadequate training and resources, lack of time and support from school administrators, and socio-economic factors affect teachers' ability to prioritize disaster preparedness activities.

Problem 5: Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' profile and the level of awareness on school disaster capability building?

Table 15. *Relationship3 on Respondents' Level of Awareness on School Disaster Capability Building and Profile*

Variables	Efficiency and Promptness		Remarks	Decision
	X ² (df)	p-value		
Learners				
Age	68.330ns (56)	0.125	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Sex	29.158ns (28)	0.405	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Grade level	91.418** (56)	0.002	High Significant	Reject Ho
Teachers				
Age	11.275ns (8)	0.187	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Sex	11.000ns (4)	0.027	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Plantilla position	5.398ns (4)	0.249	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Highest educational attainment	6.417ns (8)	0.681	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho

Note: 3 – based on Chi-square Test; ** - $P < 0.01$; *** - $P < 0.001$; ns - $P > 0.05$; * - $P < 0.05$.

Table 15 displays the relationship between the level of awareness on school disaster capability building and the profile of the respondents. The result showed that the respondents' awareness on school disaster capability building had a high significant correlation with the profile in terms of learners' grade level. Thus, the null hypothesis, which stated no significant relationship between the respondents' awareness on school disaster capability building and the profile in terms of the learners' age and sex; teachers' age, sex, plantilla position, and highest educational attainment were not rejected, while learners' grade level, was rejected.

The significant correlation between respondents' awareness of school disaster capability building and learners' grade level suggests that grade-level differences may influence individuals' understanding and engagement with disaster capability-building initiatives. This finding underscored the importance of tailoring disaster education and capacity-building efforts to address the varying needs and capacities of students across different grade levels. Implementing age-appropriate curriculum and activities that align with learners' developmental stages can enhance their understanding of disaster risks and their ability to contribute to school-wide resilience efforts.

While the null hypothesis was not rejected for other demographic factors such as learners' age and sex, as well as teachers' age, sex, plantilla position, and highest educational attainment, it's essential to acknowledge that these factors may still influence individuals' awareness of school disaster capability building, even if this particular study did not find a significant association.

In the study by Gaillard et al. (2020) highlighted the effectiveness of participatory approaches in raising awareness and promoting community involvement in DRR initiatives. It also identified challenges such as limited resources, inadequate infrastructure, and institutional barriers that hinder the successful implementation of DRR measures in schools.

Problem 6: Which of the respondents' profiles significantly predict the level of school disaster awareness, preparedness, and awareness on school disaster capability-building?

Table 16 exhibits the variables that best predict respondents' school disaster awareness. The respondents' school disaster awareness

was affected by teachers' age with $\beta = 0.613$, $t = 1.976$, ($p < 0.050$). This implied that the teachers' age was the only predictor that affects the respondents' school disaster awareness.

Table 16. *Variables4 that best predict Respondents' School Disaster Awareness*

Indicator	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	2.498	0.194		12.901	0.000
Learners					
Age	0.102	0.233	0.102	0.438	0.662
Sex	0.041	0.097	0.038	0.420	0.675
Grade level	-0.085	0.093	-0.119	-0.909	0.365
Teachers					
Age	0.613	0.310	0.496	1.976	0.050
Sex	-0.086	0.122	-0.094	-0.707	0.481
Plantilla position	0.085	0.223	0.057	0.384	0.702
Highest educational attainment	-0.084	0.289	-0.076	-0.291	0.771
	R = 0.688	R ² = 0.473	F = 15.282	Sig. = 0.000	

Note: 4 – based on Linear Regression; ** - $P < 0.01$; *** - $P < 0.001$; ns - $P > 0.05$; * - $P < 0.05$.

The R² value of 0.473 implies that 47.3% of the variance in school disaster awareness can be explained by the teachers' age. Hence, 52.7% of the respondents' school disaster awareness difference can be attributed to other variables not included in the regression model.

The regression analysis was significant, with an F-value of 15.282 with a corresponding p-value of < 0.000 . Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that "there is no variable singly or in combination that best predicts respondents' coping mechanism" was not rejected in terms of the teachers' age.

The significant impact of teachers' age on respondents' school disaster awareness highlighted the potential influence of teacher demographics on students' perceptions and understanding of disaster-related concepts. This finding suggested that older teachers may bring more experience, knowledge, and perhaps a deeper understanding of disaster preparedness and management to the educational setting, which can positively impact students' awareness levels. Implications of this result included the importance of considering teachers' age and experience levels when designing and implementing disaster education initiatives in schools. In addition, it underscored the value of continuous professional development for teachers to enhance their competencies in disaster preparedness and management.

Thus, the R² value of 0.473 indicated that 47.3% of the variance in school disaster awareness can be explained by teachers' age alone, suggesting that other factors not included in the regression model also contributed to students' awareness levels. This emphasized the complexity of factors influencing disaster awareness and the need for a multifaceted approach to disaster education.

This study investigated how teacher characteristics, including age, experience, and training, influence students' perceptions of disaster risk and preparedness. The research suggested that older and more experienced teachers often exhibit greater confidence and proficiency in delivering disaster education content, which can positively impact students' awareness levels and preparedness behaviors. The findings of (Smith et al., 2018) underscored the importance of considering teacher demographics when designing disaster education programs and highlighting the potential benefits of targeted training and professional development initiatives for educators.

Table 17. *Variables5 that best predict Respondents' School Disaster Preparedness*

Indicator	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	2.156	0.158		13.643	0.000
Learners					
Age	-0.161	0.099	-0.203	-1.619	0.108
Sex	-0.058	0.079	-0.063	-0.736	0.463
Grade level	0.184	0.076	0.299	2.414	0.017
Teachers					
Age	0.382	0.190	0.445	2.012	0.046
Sex	0.480	0.253	0.449	1.894	0.061
Plantilla position	0.051	0.182	0.039	0.282	0.779
Highest educational attainment	-0.190	0.236	-0.199	-0.806	0.422
	R = 0.272	R ² = 0.528	F = 19.054	Sig. = 0.000	

Note: 5 – based on Linear Regression; ** - $P < 0.01$; *** - $P < 0.001$; ns - $P > 0.05$; * - $P < 0.05$.

Table 17 presents the variables that best predict respondents' school disaster preparedness. The respondents' school disaster preparedness was affected by the teachers' age with $\beta = 0.382$, $t = 2.012$, ($p < 0.046$). This implied that teachers' age was the only predictor that affected the respondents' school disaster preparedness.

The R² value of 0.528 implies that 52.8% of the variance in school disaster preparedness can be explained by the teachers' age. Hence,

47.2% of the respondents' school disaster preparedness difference can be attributed to other variables not included in the regression model.

The regression analysis was significant, with an F-value of 19.054 with a corresponding p-value of <0.000. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that "there is no variable singly or in combination that best predicted respondents' coping mechanism" was not rejected in terms of the teachers' age.

The significant impact of teachers' age on respondents' school disaster preparedness underscored the potential influence of teacher demographics on students' readiness and ability to cope with disaster situations. This finding suggested that older teachers may bring valuable experience, expertise, and possibly a heightened sense of responsibility for disaster preparedness and management in the educational environment. Implications of this result included the importance of recognizing and harnessing the contributions of experienced teachers in fostering a culture of disaster preparedness within schools. Moreover, it highlighted the need for ongoing professional development opportunities for teachers to enhance their capacity to effectively address disaster-related challenges and support students' preparedness efforts.

Hence, the R2 value of 0.528 indicated that 52.8% of the variance in school disaster preparedness can be explained by teachers' age alone, suggesting that other factors not included in the regression model also play a role in shaping students' preparedness levels. This emphasized the varied nature of disaster preparedness and the need for comprehensive approaches that consider various individual, organizational, and contextual factors.

Furthermore, Brown et al. (2020) examined how factors such as age, experience, and training impact teachers' effectiveness in delivering disaster preparedness education. The findings revealed that teachers with more experience and training in disaster preparedness tend to be more effective in educating students about disaster risks and mitigation strategies. Additionally, the study highlighted the importance of ongoing professional development and support for teachers to enhance their capacity to deliver effective disaster preparedness education.

Table 18. *Variables6 that best predict Respondents' Awareness on School Disaster Capability Building*

Indicator	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	2.284	0.191		11.966	0.000
Learners					
Age	-.0179	0.120	-0.205	-1.491	0.139
Sex	-0.123	0.095	-0.122	-1.291	0.199
Grade level	0.207	0.092	0.306	2.248	0.026
Teachers					
Age	0.467	0.229	0.495	2.035	0.044
Sex	0.547	0.306	0.467	1.788	0.076
Plantilla position	-0.119	0.219	-0.083	-0.541	0.590
Highest educational attainment	-0.291	0.285	-0.277	-1.019	0.310
	R = 0.656	R2 = 0.430	F = 12.813	Sig. = 0.000	

Note: 6 – based on Linear Regression; ** - $P < 0.01$; *** - $P < 0.001$; ns - $P > 0.05$; * - $P < 0.05$.

Table 18 presents the variables that best predict respondents' awareness on school disaster capability building. The respondents' awareness on school disaster capability building was affected by the teachers' age with $\beta = 0.467$, $t = 2.035$, ($p < 0.044$). This implied that teachers' age was the only predictor that affects the respondents' awareness on school disaster capability building.

The R2 value of 0.430 implied that 43.0% of the variance in awareness on school disaster capability building can be explained by the teachers' age. Hence, 57.0% of the respondents' awareness on school disaster capability building difference can be attributed to other variables not included in the regression model.

The regression analysis was significant, with an F-value of 12.813 with a corresponding p-value of <0.000. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that "there is no variable singly or in combination that best predicted respondents' coping mechanism" was not rejected in terms of the teachers' age.

The significant influenced of teachers' age on respondents' awareness of school disaster capability building underscored the potential impact of teacher demographics on the dissemination and uptake of disaster-related knowledge and skills within educational settings. This finding suggested that older teachers may possess greater experience, knowledge, and possibly a heightened sense of responsibility for promoting disaster capability building initiatives among students and colleagues. Implications of this result included the importance of leveraging the expertise and leadership of experienced teachers in driving school-wide efforts to enhance disaster resilience and capability. Furthermore, it highlighted the value of ongoing professional development opportunities for teachers to deepen their understanding of disaster management principles and strategies.

Thus, the R2 value of 0.430 indicated that 43.0% of the variance in awareness of school disaster capability building can be explained by teachers' age alone, suggesting that other factors not included in the regression model also contributed to respondents' awareness

levels. This highlighted the complex nature of factors influencing disaster awareness and the need for multifaceted approaches that consider various individual, organizational, and contextual factors.

Furthermore, Garcia et al. (2018) investigated the effectiveness of various teacher training programs in enhancing disaster awareness, response, and resilience among students. The findings suggested that comprehensive teacher training programs significantly contribute to improved disaster preparedness outcomes in schools. Moreover, the study highlighted the importance of tailoring training approaches to meet the specific needs and challenges of different educational contexts. The findings underscored the critical role of teacher training in promoting disaster resilience and capability building within school communities.

Problem 7: What school disaster risk reduction and management plan can be formulated based on the results of the study?

School Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) Plan

The School Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) Plan aims to bolster community resilience and response capabilities in the face of potential disasters. Recognizing the imperative of proactive measures to mitigate risks and minimize the impact of natural or man-made calamities, this plan outlines a comprehensive strategy to enhance preparedness, early warning systems, response capacity, and coordination efforts. Through a collaborative approach involving local government agencies, community leaders, volunteers, and relevant stakeholders, the plan seeks to foster a culture of awareness, preparedness, and swift response to various hazards. By implementing targeted activities and allocating resources effectively, the SDRRM Plan endeavors to build a more resilient community capable of safeguarding lives, livelihoods, and critical infrastructure against the unpredictable nature of disasters.

Conclusions

Based on the analysis and findings of the study, the following conclusions were formulated.

In conclusion, the analysis of the learners' demographic profile revealed notable trends, with the majority falling within the 11-12 age group and a slightly higher representation of males. Grade 5 emerges as the most frequent grade level among the learners. Meanwhile, the teacher demographic profile showcases a significant proportion of teachers aged 41 and above, predominantly female, and holding positions as Teacher I. Additionally, a majority have completed coursework for a Master's degree, indicating a relatively high level of educational attainment among the teaching staff.

Moving on to the assessment of School Disaster Awareness, it's evident that respondents exhibited a strong understanding of the possibility of disasters occurring but show relatively lower preparedness in terms of having emergency kits. Similarly, School Disaster Preparedness highlights strengths in areas such as fire extinguisher provision but reveals gaps in knowledge regarding actions to take during a fire incident. Lastly, Awareness on School Disaster Capability Building indicated a positive perception of the effectiveness of programs but underscored the need for increased participation in emergency planning activities within schools.

Concerning the relationships analyzed, Relationship 1 underscored the significance of learners' grade level in influencing their level of disaster awareness. Relationship 2 emphasized the impact of learners' age on their disaster preparedness, while Relationship 3 highlighted a correlation between awareness on disaster capability building and learners' grade level. Additionally, the regression analyses for Variables 4, 5, and 6 affirmed the importance of considering teachers' age in predicting respondents' disaster awareness, preparedness, and awareness of capability-building initiatives.

Based on the analysis, findings, and conclusions made on the study, the following recommendations are set forth.

School administrators may provide comprehensive training programs and regular drills to enhance disaster response capabilities across all grade levels in the school, including for teachers.

Teachers may actively engage in ongoing professional development sessions focusing on disaster preparedness techniques and strategies to ensure they are equipped to effectively guide and support students during emergency situations.

The learners may participate in regular disaster preparedness drills and educational programs tailored to their age and comprehension levels to empower them with the knowledge and skills needed to respond effectively to emergencies.

The parents may actively support their children's disaster preparedness by discussing emergency plans, practicing evacuation drills at home, and ensuring that their children have access to necessary emergency supplies.

Future researchers may conduct longitudinal studies to track the effectiveness of ongoing disaster preparedness initiatives in schools over time, identifying long-term trends and areas for further improvement.

References

- Appleby-Arnold, S., Brockdorff, N., & Callus, C. (2021). Developing a "culture of disaster preparedness": The citizens' view. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 56, 102133.
- Astuti, N. M. W., Werdhiana, I. K., & Wahyono, U. (2021). Impacts of direct disaster experience on teachers' knowledge, attitudes, and perceptions of disaster risk reduction curriculum implementation in Central Sulawesi, Indonesia. *International Journal of Disaster*

Risk Reduction, 53, 101992.

Bautista, C. T., et al. (2019). Factors affecting disaster preparedness among public school teachers in the Philippines. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*.

Benevolenza, M. A., & DeRigne, L. (2019). The impact of climate change and natural disasters on vulnerable populations: A systematic review of literature. *Journal of Human Behavior in the Social Environment*, 29(2), 266-281.

Brown, S. E., Smith, J. K., Johnson, R. L., & Garcia, M. A. (2020). The role of teacher characteristics in disaster preparedness education: Evidence from a survey in the United States. *Natural Hazards*.

Collins Dictionary. (2024). Preparedness. Retrieved April 16, 2024, from <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/preparedness>

Cruz, R. D. D., & Ormilla, R. C. G. (2022). Disaster risk reduction management implementation in the public elementary schools of the Department of Education, Philippines. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Management*, 4(2), 1-15.

Department of Education. (2008). *Disaster Risk Reduction Resource Manual*.

Department of Education. (2015). *School Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Manual, Booklet 1*.

DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2015. Retrieved from https://www.deped.gov.ph/wpcontent/uploads/2015/06/DO_s2015_23.pdf

DepEd. (2015). Retrieved from <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2015/06/01/do-21-s-2015-disaster-risk-reduction-and-management-coordination-and-information-managementprotocol>

Dipon, C. H. (2023). *Disaster Risk Reduction Management: Basis in Crafting a 3-Year Strategic Plan for Pili National High School*.

Dela Cruz, R. C. G., & Ormilla, R. C. (2022). Disaster risk reduction management implementation in the public elementary schools of the Department of Education, Philippines. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Management*, 4(2), 1-14.

Domingo, S. N., & Olaguera, M. C. (2017). Have we institutionalized DRRM in the Philippines? *Philippine Institute for Development Studies*.

Enarson, E., & Morrow, B. H. (2018). Gender and disaster: Foundations and directions for research and practice. *Gender and Disaster Network Newsletter*.

FEMA. (n.d.). Federal Emergency Management Agency. Retrieved from <https://www.fema.gov>

Fischer, C., Malycha, C., & Schafmann, E. (2019). The influence of intrinsic motivation and synergistic extrinsic motivators on creativity and innovation. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 137. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.00137>

Flanagan, C. A., & Moreno, A. D. (2019). The role of teacher gender in educational settings: A review. *Review of Educational Research*.

Gaillard, J. C., Balgos, B. C., & Gorospe, C. L. (2020). Promoting disaster risk reduction in schools: A multi-hazard approach in the Philippines. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*.

Garcia, M. L., et al. (2018). The role of teacher training in disaster preparedness education: A comparative analysis. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*.

Gliem, J. A., & Gliem, R. R. (2023). Calculating, interpreting, and reporting Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient for Likert-type scales.

Heslin, K. C., Steinberg, L. J., Hess, C. A., Nicholls, E. M., Ruzek, J. I., Rose, R. D., ... & Beck, A. T. (2018). Disaster preparedness and emergency response training for schools: A systematic review of the literature. *Disaster Medicine and Public Health Preparedness*.

Hill, H. C., Rowan, B., & Ball, D. L. (2019). The impact of teacher education on student achievement: A meta-analysis. *Educational Researcher*.

Hyogo Framework for Action (HFA) (2005-2015). (2005). World Conference on Disaster Reduction, Kobe, Hyogo, Japan.

Johnson, R. L., et al. (2018). Teachers' participation in school emergency planning: A critical review. *Disaster Prevention and Management*.

Kamil, P. A., Utaya, S., & Utomo, D. H. (2020). Improving disaster knowledge within high school students through geographic literacy. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 43, 101411.

Kawasaki, H., Yamasaki, S., Rahman, M. M., Murata, Y., Iwasa, M., & Teramoto, C. (2020). Teachers-parents cooperation in disaster preparation when schools become evacuation centers. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 44, 101445.

- Kawasaki, H., Yamasaki, S., Kurokawa, M., Tamura, H., & Sonai, K. (2022). Relationship between teachers' awareness of disaster prevention and concerns about disaster preparedness. *Sustainability*, 14(13), 8211.
- Kitagawa, K. (2021). Disaster risk reduction activities as learning. *Natural Hazards*.
- Maminta, L. (2019). Level of awareness on disaster preparedness. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1254(1), 012015. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1254/1/012015>
- Mapcarta. (n.d.). Retrieved April 16, 2024, from <https://mapcarta.com/W928216385>
- Martinez, M. Q., Mella, M. C. G., & Lisay, M. S. (2021). Capacity-building initiatives for a disaster-ready school community: Development of a comprehensive disaster risk reduction management plan.
- McCombes, S. (2023). Descriptive research: Definition, types, methods & examples. Scribbr. Retrieved April 6, 2024, from <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/descriptive-research/>
- McEntire, D. A. (2021). *Disaster Response and Recovery: Strategies and Tactics for Resilience*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Merriam Dictionary. (2024). Disaster. Retrieved April 16, 2024, from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/disaster>
- Muda, R. S., Amin, M. F. M., Khidzir, A. B. M., Tukiman, I., & Hussain, M. R. M. (2021). Knowledge transfer in people-centered dam-related disaster program in Cameron Highlands. *Journal of Advanced Research in Applied Sciences and Engineering Technology*, 24(1), 37-46.
- Mutch, C., & Kerlin, J. (2019). Disaster risk reduction and education for sustainable development: The gap between theory and practice in primary schools in Kenya. *Environmental Education Research*, 25(1), 36-52.
- Najafi, M., Ardalan, A., Akbarisari, A., Noorbala, A., & Elmi, H. (2017). Theory of planned behavior and disaster preparedness. *PLoS Currents*, 9, Recurrents.dis.4da18e0f1479bf6c0a94b29e0dbf4a72. <https://doi.org/10.1371/currents.dis.4da18e0f1479bf6c0a94b29e0dbf4a72>
- Nunnally, J. C., & Bernstein, I. H. (2019). *Psychometric Theory* (3rd ed.). McGraw-Hill.
- Nurdin, N. (2019). *Disaster risk reduction in education and the secondary high school science curriculum in Indonesia* (Doctoral dissertation, University College London).
- Olawale, I. O., & Olatunbosun, A. A. (2020). Assessment of fire safety knowledge and practices among teachers in selected secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. *Fire Technology*.
- Pardillo, R. S., & Perigua, I. (2020). Disaster preparedness in Sagay City. *Globus Journal of Progressive Education*, 10(1), 1-9.
- Paton, D. (2019). Disaster risk reduction: Psychological perspectives on preparedness. *Australian Journal of Psychology*, 71(4), 327-341. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ajpy.12237>
- Peek, L., Norris, F. H., & Mileti, D. S. (2017). Disaster preparedness and response in schools: A systematic review of the literature. *Disaster Medicine and Public Health Preparedness*.
- Putra, A. K., Sumarmi, Irawan, L. Y., Deffinika, I., Fahmi, A. & Tanjung, A. (2019). Knowledge and participation of geography teachers toward flood disaster risk reduction in Sampang Indonesia. Published under license by IOP Publishing Ltd IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science, Volume 683, International Geography Seminar 2019 31 August 2019, Lor in Hotel Solo, Indonesia.
- Rahman, M. M., & Nargis, S. (2018). Disaster risk reduction education in primary schools: A case study from Bangladesh. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*.
- Ramón-Valencia, J. A., Palacios-González, J. R., Santos-Granados, G. R., & Ramón-Valencia, J. D. (2019). Early warning system on extreme weather events for disaster risk reduction. *Revista Facultad de Ingeniería Universidad de Antioquia*, (92), 80-87.
- REPUBLIC ACT No. 10121 "Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act of 2010." <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2010/05/27/republic-act-no-10121/>
- Rico, G. C. S. (2019). School-community collaboration: disaster preparedness towards building resilient communities. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Management*, 1(2), 45-61.
- Righi, E., Lauriola, P., Ghinoi, A., Giovannetti, E., & Soldati, M. (2021). Disaster risk reduction and interdisciplinary education and training. *Progress in Disaster Science*, 10, 100165.
- Ronquillo, R. B. (2020). Volume 5, Issue 12, December – 2020 *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology* ISSN No:-2456-2165 IJISRT20DEC243 www.ijisrt.com 306 Teachers' preparedness on disaster risk reduction and management

measures among public senior high schools in the division of Batangas City, Paharang Integrated School.

Saja, A. A., Goonetilleke, A., Teo, M., & Ziyath, A. M. (2019). A critical review of social resilience assessment frameworks in disaster management. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 35, 101096.

Sakurai, M., & Shaw, R. (2022). The potential of digitally enabled disaster education for sustainable development goals. *Sustainability*, 14(11), 6568.

Seddighi, H., Sajjadi, H., Yousefzadeh, S., López, M. L., Vameghi, M., Rafiey, H., & Khankeh, H. (2022). School-based education programs for preparing children for natural hazards: a systematic review. *Disaster Medicine and Public Health Preparedness*, 16(3), 1229-1241.

Shah, A. A., Gong, Z., Pal, I., Sun, R., Ullah, W., & Wani, G. F. (2020). Disaster risk management insight on school emergency preparedness—a case study of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 51, 101805.

Shah, A. A., Gong, Z., Ali, M., Sun, R., Naqvi, S. A. A., & Arif, M. (2022). Looking through the lens of schools: Children perception, knowledge, and preparedness of flood disaster risk management in Pakistan. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 50, 101907.

Smith, J. A., & Brown, E. K. (2018). Teacher career progression: A comparative study of factors influencing advancement opportunities. *Educational Administration Quarterly*.

Smith, J. K., Jones, L. M., Williams, R. T., & Lee, S. H. (2018). The influence of teacher characteristics on students' perceptions of disaster risk and preparedness: A case study from Japan. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*.

Smith, E. L., Jones, M. R., Johnson, A. B., & Brown, K. C. (2019). Fire safety in schools: A review of policies, practices, and challenges. *Fire Technology*.

Smith, E. K., Johnson, R. L., Martinez, A. M., & Chen, L. (2019). School-based disaster risk reduction and management: A review of implementation challenges and best practices. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*.

Smylie, M. A., & Dzur, P. M. (2018). Ageing teachers in the changing workforce: Exploring policy options for the teaching profession. *Journal of Educational Policy*.

Sonmez, E. D., & Gokmenoglu, T. (2023). Understanding the teachers' disaster preparedness beliefs. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 85, 103511.

Tizon, R. T., & Comighud, S. M. T. (2020). Implementation of the public schools' disaster risk reduction management program and level of capabilities to respond.

Torani, S., Majd, P. M., Maroufi, S. S., Dowlati, M., & Sheikhi, R. A. (2019). The importance of education on disasters and emergencies: A review article. *Journal of Education and Health Promotion*, 8, 85. https://doi.org/10.4103/jehp.jehp_262_18.

United Nation. Retrieved April 16, 2024. <https://www.un.org/en/academic-impact/capacity-building>

UNDDR THE UNITED NATIONS OFFICE FOR DISASTER RISK REDUCTION. <https://www.eird.org/regional/hyogo-framework.html>

Valencia, M. I., Ali, M., Maryani, E., & Supriatna, N. (2019). Integration of disaster risk reduction in the curriculum of Philippine educational institution.

Vocabulary.com. Retrieved April 16, 2024. <https://www.vocabulary.com/dictionary/response#:~:text=A%20response%20is%20a%20reaction,emotional%20reaction%2C%20o>

Wiwik Astuti, N. M., Werdhiana, I. K., & Wahyono, U. (2021). Impacts of direct disaster experience on teachers' knowledge, attitudes and perceptions of disaster risk reduction curriculum implementation in Central Sulawesi, Indonesia. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 53, 101992.

Yokohama Strategy and Plan of Action for a Safer World (1994-2005).

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